

The first record of *Dusmetia euripersia* Trjapitzin (Chalcidoidea: Encyrtidae) from Ukraine

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Simutnik, S.A. The first record of *Dusmetia euripersia* Trjapitzin (Chalcidoidea: Encyrtidae) from Ukraine. Summary. The second species of the genus *Dusmetia*, *D. euripersia* Trjapitzin 1962 described from Armenia, is recorded in the fauna of Ukraine for the first time. New locations of *D. pulex* (Ruschka, 1923), previously registered only from Cherkasy Region, are recorded. High resolution photomicrographs of the both Ukrainian species are given.

Key words: Encyrtidae, *Dusmetia euripersia*, *D. pulex*, Ukraine.

Симутнік, С.А. Перша знахідка *Dusmetia euripersia* Trjapitzin (Chalcidoidea: Encyrtidae) в Україні. Резюме. Другий вид роду *Dusmetia*, описаний з Вірменії *D. euripersia* Тряпичин 1962, вперше зареєстровано в фауні України. Для відміченого раніше лише з Черкаської області *D. pulex* (Ruschka, 1923) наведені нові точки знаходок. Презентовано фотомікрографії високого розділення обох українських видів.

Ключові слова: Encyrtidae, *Dusmetia euripersia*, *D. pulex*, Ukraine.

Симутник, С. А. Первая находка *Dusmetia euripersia* Trjapitzin (Chalcidoidea: Encyrtidae) в Украине. Резюме. Второй вид рода *Dusmetia*, описанный из Армении *D. euripersia* Тряпичин 1962, впервые зарегистрирован в фауне Украины. Для отмеченного ранее только из Черкасской области *D. pulex* (Ruschka, 1923) приведены новые точки находок. Даны фотомикрографии высокого разрешения обоих украинских видов.

Ключевые слова: Encyrtidae, *Dusmetia euripersia*, *D. pulex*, Ukraine.

Introduction

The genus *Dusmetia* Mercet, 1921 belongs to the subfamily Tetracneminae, majority of which are parasitoids of Pseudococcidae. In the world fauna are known six species of the genus (Noyes, 2018). *D. pulex* (Ruschka, 1923) (*Blastothrix pulex*) only was recorded earlier from Ukraine (Cherkasy Region) (Trjapitzin, 1989).

I appreciate kindness of Galina Stetsun, who collects the one female of *D. euripersia* to Moericke trap on the Dzharylgach island, and Victor Fursov for Belgorod Region's material.

Material and methods

The material is deposited in I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, National Academy of Sciences of

Ukraine (Kyiv). Specimens were identified using keys of Trjapitzin (1989).

The original photographs were taken using a Leica Z16 APO stereomicroscope equipped with a Leica DFC 450 camera and processed with LAS V3.8 software. Some images were digitally retouched using Adobe Photoshop.

Dusmetia pulex (Ruschka, 1923) (Figs 1–15)

Material. Ukraine: Kyiv Region, Kyiv, Lysa Hora (Vyubichi), 14.06.2000., 1♂ (S. Simutnik) (SIZK); Crimea, Dzhankoy District, vicinity of Pridorozhnoye, forbs, 2.06.2003., 1♀, (S. Simutnik) (SIZK); Kherson Region, Novotroitsky District, Sivash lake, Churyuk island 7.06.2003., 1♀, 1♂ (S. Simutnik) (SIZK); Crimea, Karadag Reserve, Karadag valley, 16.08.2005., 1♀, 1♂ (S. Simutnik) (SIZK). **Russia:** Belgorod Region, Central Black Earth Reserve, Yamskaya Steppe plot, 12.07.1985., 2♂ (V. Fursov) (SIZK).

Figs 1–8. *Dusmetia pulex*, ♀, (full winged form). 1 — habitus, lateral view; 2 — dorsal view; 3 — forewing; 4 — venation of forewing; 5 — head and mesosoma, ventrolateral view; 6 — head, frontal view; 7 — mesosoma, dorsal view; 8 — head and mesosoma, dorsal view.

Distribution. East Palearctic, Great Britain, Finland, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Austria, Sweden, Hungary, Romania, Moldova, Central European Russia, Kostroma Region (Trjapitzin, 1989; Fauna Europea, 2019), Belgorod Region (**first record**), Primorsky Territory, Kazakhstan: Ural Region, Mongolia. Ukraine: Cherkasy Region

(Trjapitzin, 1989), Kyiv Region (**first record**), Kherson Region (**first record**), Crimea (**first record**).

Variations. Full-winged and short-winged specimens are known (Figs 1, 9). One, two or three of the last segments of funicle can be white (Figs 9, 15).

Figs 9–15. *Dusmetia pulex*, (short winged forms). 9, 11, 13 — ♀ with F6 white, 9 — habitus, lateral view; 11 — dorsolateral view; 13 — head, antennae, frontal view; 10, 12, 14 — ♂, 10, 12 — habitus, lateral view; 14 — dorsal view; 15 — ♀ with F4-F6 white, dorsolateral view. F(1–6) — funicle segment.

Dusmetia euripersia Trjapitzin 1962 (Figs 16–19)

Material. Ukraine: Kherson Region, Skadovsk, Dzharylgach island, 46.02N, 32.90E, 19.06.2019, 1♀ (G. Stetsun) (SIZK).

Distribution. Armenia (Trjapitzin, 1962, 1989). Ukraine (**first record**): Kherson Region.

Note. The rudiments of the forewings with a transversely truncated apex (Fig. 19) are well different from the rest of the species of the genus.

Figs 16–19. *Dusmetia euripersia*, ♀. 16 — habitus, lateral view; 17 — head, frontal view; 18 — dorsal view; 19 — rudiment of forewing (is shown by arrow).

References

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